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MILESTONE REPORT

EXPERIMENTAL PHYSICS GOALS CAPTURED

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Abstract:

Experimental physics goals documented in form of presentations on Indico (Green). Contributions for Open Access proceedings publication with SN (Gold) approved. User community survey on R&D topics, priorities and collaboration potentials considering geographical distribution and topical complementarity launched.

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1. EXPERIMENTAL PHYSICS GOALS OF FCC

The LHC experiments have so far confirmed with high accuracy (up to energies of several TeV) the validity of the Standard Model, the basic theory that describes the fundamental building blocks of visible matter and their interactions. Furthermore, in 2012 the ATLAS and CMS experiments discovered the Higgs boson, a new particle with a mass of 125 GeV that is the cornerstone of the Standard Model. Furthermore the absence of signs of new physics in our experimental searches, test previously proposed models for new physics and give rise to new approaches. Thanks to the LHC, particle physics has arrived at an important moment of its history calling for a new research infrastructure, like the proposed FCC, that will offer the broadest research programme in the most efficient way.

1.1. INTERMEDIATE FUTURE: A FUTURE CIRCULAR LEPTON COLLIDER (FCC-EE)

Searching for BSM physics directly through new particle production or indirectly through precision measurements is a vibrant and evolving field. It is a primary science driver in high-energy physics, and the energy frontier provides many unique approaches and discovery opportunities. The energy frontier casts a wide net across thousands of searches and observables. These can be interpreted in the context of complete top-down models and more model-independent ad-hoc simplified models. Furthermore, the frontier provides an opportunity to directly constrain or discover possible dark matter candidates and associated sectors. The energy frontier has laid out a vision for the immediate, intermediate, and long-term future. For BSM physics, each phase would provide significant new insights into fundamental physics and discovery potential.

The $e\text{-}e$ Higgs factory envisioned in the Energy Frontier report will provide several potential avenues for discovery. Precision measurements of Higgs properties are sensitive to BSM physics regardless of the direct production signature. In some cases, they are sensitive to BSM physics that may be beyond the reach of the HL-LHC or even higher-energy colliders. The clean, large sample of Higgses will provide unique access to exotic Higgs decays, which a hadron collider may find challenging to identify. Such a machine can see most new direct production processes below $\sqrt{s}/2$ and have indirect sensitivity to higher energy scales. Very large luminosities at lower energies, such as the Z-pole, or near the top-quark pair and WW thresholds can also provide high-precision measurements which indirectly constrain new physics (e.g., the W-mass). Such samples would also significantly increase constraints on moderate-energy, weakly-coupled phenomena such as dark photons.

1.2. LONG-TERM FUTURE: A MULTI-TeV HADRON CIRCULAR COLLIDER (FCC-HH)

In the longer term, a multi-TeV machine could provide the largest and most comprehensive increase in the BSM discovery reach of the energy frontier. The reach would dramatically increase in almost all categories for both model-dependent and model-independent searches. At the 100 TeV regime, the thermal WIMP target could be reached for minimal WIMP candidates (e.g., Higgsino- and Wino-like models with no other relevant particles), which is representative of the power of the experiments.

A discovery machine would push constraints on the Higgs-mass scale naturalness by the square of the increase in energy reach, which is potentially two orders of magnitude beyond the HL-LHC. It could open up access to new hidden sectors by producing a substantially higher mediator mass or probing even smaller couplings. The reach of each of the proposed colliders differs in non-trivial ways, as has been summarized in this document for various representative cases. To realize such a machine, a strong R&D program for both accelerators and detectors is critical, with continued tight interaction between the Accelerator, Instrumentation, and Energy Frontiers.

In brief, there are several reasons why physics beyond the Standard Model (BSM) of particle physics is likely and, in some cases, unavoidable. Searching for them requires the widest possible experimental programme offered by the combination of a lepton and a circular collider providing precision and direct detection opportunities. A subset of the most relevant questions to energy frontier approaches can be grouped in three broad categories:

Phenomena that have been observed but where a fundamental explanation is still lacking.
What is the fundamental composition of Dark Matter?
What is the additional source of CP violation needed to explain the matter-antimatter asymmetry observed in the universe?
Possible observations of BSM physics referred to broadly as Anomalies that underlie the strong connection of the energy frontier to the rare and intensity frontiers.
Cosmological tensions, such as the Hubble tension, which might indicate new particles.
How is particle physics unified with gravity?
Guiding principles forming the basis of the successful stories behind the current Standard Model (SM)
Naturalness considerations underlying our hunt for BSM physics and how future colliders address these puzzles.
The flavour structure of the SM is complex and begs for an underlying explanation. This may be related to questions regarding the scale/origin of electroweak symmetry breaking and the Higgs mechanism
Why are neutrinos so light? What is the mechanism of their mass generation?
Why is there no CP violation in the strong force?
Is there a simpler "grand unified" theory unifying gauge couplings and/or quarks and leptons?
History has shown many times that particle physics should maintain a wide open view for possible new phenomena that might not fit in the simplest theoretical extensions of the SM.
Are there new interactions or new particles around or above the electroweak scale?
Is lepton universality violated?
Are there long-lived or feebly-interacting particles which have evaded traditional BSM searches?
Broad question of how to reduce biases in our searches and conduct them in a more model-independent way.

The FCC-ee will be implemented in stages as an electroweak, flavour, Higgs, and top factory by spanning the energy range from the Z pole and the WW threshold through the maximum Higgs production rate, up to the $t\bar{t}$ threshold and beyond. The high luminosity at the Z pole opens a unique domain for new particle searches. The envisioned 15-year experimental programme is summarized in

the table below. The option to run on the Higgs resonance at 125 GeV, as well as the possibility to operate four interaction points, are under investigation.

Working point	Z, years 1-2	Z, later	WW	HZ	tt ⁻	(s-channel H)
$s\sqrt{\text{ (GeV)}}$	88, 91, 94		157, 163	240	340–350	365 m_H
Lumi/IP (10 ³⁴ cm ⁻² s ⁻¹)	115	230	28	8.5	0.95	1.55 (30)
Lumi/year (ab ⁻¹ , 2 IP)	24	48	6	1.7	0.2	0.34 (7)
Physics goal (ab ⁻¹)	150		10	5	0.2	1.5 (20)
Run time (year)	2	2	2	3	1	4 (3)
				10 ⁶ HZ	10 ⁶ tt ⁻	
Number of events	5×10 ¹² Z		10 ⁸ WW	+	+200k HZ	(6000)

			25k WW→H	+50k WW→H	
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Table 1. Baseline FCC-ee operation model, showing the centre-of-mass energies, instantaneous luminosities for each IP, integrated luminosity per year summed over the 2 IPs corresponding to 185 days of physics per year and 75% efficiency

Event statistics :						E _{CM} errors:
Z peak	E _{cm} : 91 GeV	5 10 ¹²	e+e- → Z	LEP x 10 ⁵		100 keV
WW threshold	E _{cm} : 161 GeV	10 ⁸	e+e- → WW	LEP x 2.10 ³		300 keV
ZH threshold	E _{cm} : 240 GeV	10 ⁶	e+e- → ZH	Never done		1 MeV
tt threshold	E _{cm} : 350 GeV	10 ⁶	e+e- → tt	Never done		2 MeV

Table 2: The energy range and the expected statistics and the four different runs foreseen for the FCC-ee as compared to the statistics previously reached at LEP. The last column also shows the estimated uncertainty in measuring the centre-of-mass energy at the two beams of FCC-ee for the different runs.

An across-the-board exploration of these three aspects can be performed effectively with the FCC-ee operating at different centre-of-mass energies. Measurements of small deviations of Higgs properties or of precision electroweak observables benefit from the unprecedented luminosities offered at the FCC-ee. The sensitivity of these measurements to heavy new physics can be quantified with a global EFT fit, as shown in Fig.XX This figure highlights (i) the complementarity of Higgs and electroweak measurements; and (ii) the need of more statistics for the (statistics-limited) Higgs measurements, thus confirming the potential benefits of combining optimally the ILC and FCC-ee data.

Figure 1 - Electroweak (red) and Higgs (green) constraints from FCC-ee, and their combination (blue) in a global EFT fit. The constraints are presented as the 95% probability bounds on the interaction scale, $\Delta/\sqrt{c_i}$, associated to each EFT operator. Darker shades of each colour indicate the results when neglecting all SM theory uncertainties

Electroweak (red) and Higgs (green) constraints from FCC-ee, and their combination (blue) in a global EFT fit. The constraints are presented as the 95% probability bounds on the interaction scale, $\Lambda/\sqrt{c_i}$, associated to each EFT operator. Darker shades of each colour indicate the results when neglecting all SM theory uncertainties

1.3. GOAL: HIGGS BOSON PROPERTIES

The original motivation for an electron-positron circular collider was to create a high-luminosity Higgs Factory, operating at the energy of the $e^+e^- \rightarrow ZH$ cross-section maximum. Circular colliders operating at the maximum of the ZH cross section are very efficient Higgs factories, requiring ~ 9 (5) GJ per Higgs boson for FCC-ee with 2 (4) IPs at 240 GeV, vs ~ 50 GJ for the proposed ILC run plan at 250 GeV.

The total ZH cross section can be determined independently of the Higgs boson detailed properties by counting events with an identified Z boson, and for which the mass recoiling against the Z clusters around the Higgs boson mass. This model-independent measurement of g_{HZZ} , the coupling of the Higgs boson to the Z, is unique to e^+e^- colliders, and can be used as a “standard candle” by all other measurements, including those made at hadron colliders.

Obtaining a model-independent determination of the Higgs total width Γ_H by combining the above with measurements of the rate of HZ events with a $H \rightarrow ZZ^*$ decay.

The full list of precision that will be reached in measuring the Higgs interaction with the other known particles of the Standard Model is detailed in the table below (Table 3).

Collider	HL-LHC	FCC-ee _{240→365}	FCC-INT
Lumi (ab^{-1})	3	5 + 0.2 + 1.5	30
Years	10	3 + 1 + 4	25
g_{HZZ} (%)	1.5	0.18/0.17	0.17/0.16
g_{HWW} (%)	1.7	0.44/0.41	0.20/0.19
g_{Hbb} (%)	5.1	0.69/0.64	0.48/0.48
g_{Hcc} (%)	SM	1.3/1.3	0.96/0.96
g_{Hgg} (%)	2.5	1.0/0.89	0.52/0.5
$g_{H\tau\tau}$ (%)	1.9	0.74/0.66	0.49/0.46
$g_{H\mu\mu}$ (%)	4.4	8.9/3.9	0.43/0.43
$g_{H\gamma\gamma}$ (%)	1.8	3.9/1.2	0.32/0.32
$g_{HZ\gamma}$ (%)	11	-/10	0.71/0.7
g_{Htt} (%)	3.4	10./3.1	1.0/0.95
g_{HHH} (%)	50	44/33 27/24	3-4
Γ_H (%)	SM	1.1	0.91
BR_{inv} (%)	1.9	0.19	0.024
BR_{EXO} (%)	SM (0.0)	1.1	1

Table 3. Precision on the Higgs boson couplings from in the κ framework without (first numbers) and with (second numbers) HL-LHC projections, for the FCC-ee and the complete FCC integrated programme (including both the FCC-hh and the FCC-ep option). All numbers are in % and indicate 68% C.L. sensitivities. Also indicated are the standalone precision on the total decay width, and the 95% C.L. sensitivity on the “invisible” and “exotic” branching fractions. The precision on the Higgs self-coupling comprises the value extracted from the ZH and $WW \rightarrow H$ cross sections for FCC-ee, with two (top line) or four (lower line) interaction points. The precision for FCC-hh has been updated using the most recent projections from double-Higgs production at FCC-hh.

Finally, the FCC-ee stands out among the proposed future “Higgs Factories” (ILC, CLIC) for its unique opportunity to access the Higgs boson coupling to electrons through the resonant production process $e^+e^- \rightarrow H$ at $\sqrt{s}=125$ GeV. This measurement relies on the combination of the high luminosity and monochromatization of the beams, and is under study. This is a unique opportunity of FCC-ee, and one of its toughest challenges.

1.4. GOAL: PRECISION MEASUREMENTS

Several experimental facts require extensions of the Standard Model, in particular: the dominance of matter over antimatter in the Universe; the evidence for dark matter from astronomical and cosmological observations; and, closer to particle physics, the smallness of the neutrino masses, about 10^{-7} times smaller than that of the electron. The possible solutions to these questions seem to require the existence of new particles or phenomena that can occur over an immense range of mass scales and coupling strengths. The discovery of new particles, before their actual observation, has often been guided in the past by predictions based on a long history of experiments and of theory maturation. In this context, a decisive improvement of the electroweak precision observable (EWPO) measurements, combined with other precision measurements of the properties of the Higgs boson, the top quark as well as b and c hadrons and the tau lepton, could play a crucial role, by integrating sensitivity to a large range of new physics possibilities. The observation of significant deviation(s) from the Standard Model predictions would definitely be a discovery. A high significance requires not only a considerable improvement in experimental and theoretical precision, but also a large set of measured observables, in order to eliminate spurious deviations; and possibly reveal a pattern of deviations, enabling the guidance of theoretical interpretation. Improved precision equates discovery potential. It also challenges both theory and experiment. The expected statistical precision for EWPOs measured at the Z pole is typically 500 times smaller than the current uncertainties. Moreover, for the first time, a direct measurement of $\alpha_{\text{QED}}(m_Z)$ will be possible with $O(10^{-3})$ precision.

A list of electroweak observables that will be precisely measured at the FCC-ee, thus allowing to probe new physics, even physics lying at higher energies, is summarized in the table below (Table 4).

Observable	Present value \pm error	FCC-ee stat.	FCC-ee syst.	Comment and leading exp. error
$m_Z(\text{keV})$	91186700 ± 2200	4	100	From Z line shape scan
				Beam energy calibration
$\Gamma_Z(\text{keV})$	2495200 ± 2300	4	25	From Z line shape scan
				Beam energy calibration
$\sin 2\theta_{\text{Weff}}(\times 10^6)$	231480 ± 160	2	2.4	from $\text{AFB}_{\mu\mu}$ at Z peak
				Beam energy calibration
$1/\alpha_{\text{QED}}(m_Z)(\times 10^3)$	128952 ± 14	3	Small	From $\text{AFB}_{\mu\mu}$ off peak

				QED &EW errors dominate
$R\ell Z (\times 10^3)$	20767 ± 25	0.06	0.2–1	Ratio of hadrons to leptons
				Acceptance for leptons
$\alpha s(m_Z^2) (\times 10^4)$	1196 ± 30	0.1	0.4–1.6	From $R\ell Z$ above
$\sigma_{had0} (\times 10^3) \text{ (nb)}$	41541 ± 37	0.1	4	Peak hadronic cross section
				Luminosity measurement
$N_\nu (\times 10^3)$	2996 ± 7	0.005	1	Z peak cross sections
				Luminosity measurement
$R_b (\times 10^6)$	216290 ± 660	0.3	< 60	Ratio of bb^- to hadrons
				Stat. extrapol. from SLD
$A_{FB}^{b,0} (\times 10^4)$	992 ± 16	0.02	1–3	b-quark asymmetry at Z pole
				From jet charge
$A_{FB}^{pol,\tau} (\times 10^4)$	1498 ± 49	0.15	<2	τ polarization asymmetry
				τ decay physics
τ lifetime (fs)	290.3 ± 0.5	0.001	0.04	Radial alignment
τ mass (MeV)	1776.86 ± 0.12	0.004	0.04	Momentum scale
τ leptonic ($\mu\nu\mu\nu\tau$) B.R. (%)	17.38 ± 0.04	0.0001	0.003	e/μ /hadron separation
mW (MeV)	80350 ± 15	0.25	0.3	From WW threshold scan
				Beam energy calibration

Γ_W (MeV)	2085 ± 42	1.2	0.3	From WW threshold scan
				Beam energy calibration
$\alpha_s(m_W^2)(\times 10^4)$	1170 ± 420	3	Small	from R_{EW}
$N_\nu(\times 10^3)$	2920 ± 50	0.8	Small	Ratio of invis. to leptonic
				in radiative Z returns
m_{top} (MeV/c ²)	172740 ± 500	17	Small	From tt^- threshold scan
				QCD errors dominate
Γ_{top} (MeV/c ²)	1410 ± 190	45	Small	From tt^- threshold scan
				QCD errors dominate
$\lambda_{top}/\lambda_{topSM}$	1.2 ± 0.3	0.10	Small	From tt^- threshold scan
				QCD errors dominate
ttZ couplings	$\pm 30\%$	0.5–1.5%	Small	From s=365 GeV run

Table 4. Measurement of selected precision measurements at FCC-ee, compared with present precision. Statistical errors are indicated in boed phase. The systematic uncertainties are initial estimates, aim is to improve down to statistical errors. This set of measurements, together with those of the Higgs properties, achieves indirect sensitivity to new physics up to a scale Λ of 70 TeV in a description with dim 6 operators, and possibly much higher in specific new physics (non-decoupling) models.

1.5. GOAL: FLAVOURS

A total of 10×10^{12} bb^- pairs, available with a sample of 5×10^{12} Z decays promised by FCC-ee, provides many opportunities in flavour physics. This will challenge the precisions of CKM matrix element measurements expected from LHCb and Belle2, and push forward the search for unobserved phenomena such as CP-symmetry breaking in the mixing of beautiful neutral mesons.

In parallel, searches for rare decays make FCC-ee a direct discovery machine. Lepton-flavour-violating (LFV) Z decays; rare and LFV τ decays; searches for heavy neutral leptons; and rare b-hadron decays

have been explored as benchmark or flagship searches. They are illustrative of the unique potential of a high-luminosity Z factory. The discovery potential relies on the vertexing capabilities of the experiments, to benefit from the boosted topologies at the Z energy, but is mostly limited by the statistical size of the event sample.

Tau physics at the Z pole provides, still today, the most powerful tests of lepton universality and of the PMNS matrix unitarity. The increase of statistics by five orders of magnitude with respect to LEP should allow much improvement of these constraints, by combining measurements of the tau lifetime, the tau mass, and the leptonic branching ratios. These measurements provide important constraints on e.g., light-heavy neutrino mixing. Similar improvements are expected from the better precision of the invisible Z decay width measurement.

The energy evolution of event shapes and fragmentation functions also provide powerful tests of QCD in lepton collisions. The wide range of energies covered by FCC-ee, which can start at centre-of-mass energies as low as 30 GeV.

The exploration of the flavour physics program of FCC-ee is certainly in its infancy and can be expected to develop strongly in the future.

1.6. GOAL: QCD

Most of what is known of the top quark today comes from hadron colliders. In lepton collisions, the region of the top-pair threshold, and immediately above, is covered by both FCC-ee and ILC, with similar luminosity and energy efficiency.

The main output of a run at the top-pair threshold is the precise measurement of the top-quark mass, which is an essential input to reduce parametric uncertainties in the electroweak precision measurements. The aforementioned precise $\alpha_S(m_Z)$ measurement at FCC-ee reduces the corresponding parametric uncertainty of the top mass measurement at the top-pair threshold, otherwise dominant e.g. at ILC alone. Running above the top-pair threshold, $\sqrt{s} = 365$ GeV for FCC-ee and 500 GeV for ILC3, enables in addition the precise measurement of the top-quark couplings to the Z boson and the photon. This measurement is essential for the precise determination of the top Yukawa coupling at FCC-hh, through the measurement of the $t\text{-}\bar{t} \rightarrow H$ to $t\text{-}\bar{t} \rightarrow Z$ cross-section ratio.

The energy evolution of event shapes and fragmentation functions also provide powerful tests of QCD in electron-positron collisions. The wide range of energies covered by FCC-ee, which can start at centre-of-mass energies as low as 30 GeV, will provide yet another and completely independent determination of the strong coupling constant with a precision in the 10^{-4} order.

Finally, the Higgs run of FCC-ee contains an original gem: the possibility of clearly separating the $H \rightarrow gg$ decay mode of the Higgs boson from the other hadronic decays expected to be completely dominated by $b\bar{b}$ and $c\bar{c}$ decays, could provide a unique laboratory to study the gluon fragmentation in a context unaffected by colour connection to quarks.

Figure 2 - Expected relative precision on the Zt_L and Zt_R couplings at LHC (lighter green), HL-LHC (darker green), ILC at 500 GeV (blue) and FCC-ee (orange, red). The right panel shows a zoom of the left panel in the $\pm 10\%$ window. Typical deviations from the standard model in various new physics models are represented by the purple dots. The black dots indicate the deviations expected for different parameter choices of 4D Composite Higgs Models, with mass scale up to 2 TeV. For FCC-ee, the orange ellipse is obtained from an analysis of the lepton angular and energy distributions, while the smaller red ellipse is obtained if the angular and energy distributions of the b jets can be exploited.

1.7. GOAL: DIRECT OBSERVATION OF FEEBLY INTERACTING PARTICLES

Direct observation of new particles might require diverse searches and colliders to cover many orders of magnitude of coupling strength and mass scales. Feebly interacting particles such as axion-like particles, or dark photons, with masses smaller than the Z mass, may have the best odds of being found at the intensity frontier, i.e., with FCC-ee running at the Z pole, while high-energy machines might see them if their couplings are larger. The case of the axion-like particles is illustrated in the figure below. and demonstrates the high sensitivity of the Z factory FCC-ee, as well as its complementarity with the FCC-eh and with a high-energy linear lepton collider.

Figure 3 - Expected sensitivity to axion-like particles in various future facilities. The reach of FCC-ee is down to very small couplings in Z decays, while the reach of linear colliders is at higher masses for somewhat larger couplings.

Another well-motivated example of new physics is provided by neutrinos. Many neutrino mass models naturally predict the existence of heavy neutrino states, called Heavy Neutral Leptons (HNL, mostly “right-handed” or “sterile”) which mix with the known light, active neutrinos

Since both light and heavy neutrino masses are unknown, a rather large range of mixing angles should be explored. These scenarios have several possible consequences: (i) the direct observation of a long-lived HNL in Z, W, and Higgs decays and in tau, b- or c-hadron semi-leptonic decays, both mass and mixing sensitive; (ii) the mixing of the light neutrinos with heavier states, which leads to a violation of the SM relations in EWPOs; the corresponding sensitivity only depends on the mixing angle, and extends to very high masses; (iii) the violation of lepton universality in τ , b or c-hadron decays at the Z factory; (iv) a smaller-than-expected Z invisible decay width; and (v) a lepton-number violation can also result from Heavy-Neutral-Lepton production or exchange in high-energy processes at a hadron collider or a high-energy lepton collider.

2. PRESENTATIONS & PUBLICATIONS

Following the submission of M5.1, the FCC study office at CERN continued working together with the FCCIS partners, Springer/Nature and Overleaf to produce a special issue of The European Physical Journal - Plus (EPJ Plus) as an Open Access (Gold) publication focusing on the challenges and opportunities of a future electroweak and Higgs factory like the proposed FCC-ee.

The published essays document the substantial progress that has been made in the past years to understand the physics potential. They also reflect on the required detector technologies profiting from previous work for several linear colliders that have been proposed since the early 1990’s, and have been studied in extensive simulations and paper studies. Following the essays published in the previous reporting period, 12 new essays were published in 2022. This work, supported by the FCCIS project, proved pivotal for preparing the FCC community whitepaper that was submitted to the Snowmass

process; a bottom-up approach to identify the priorities of the US particle physics community [see more: <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2203.06520.pdf>]

In addition, FCCIS WP5, launched a new series of Open Access papers in the Journal: EPJ Techniques & Instrumentation <https://epjtechniquesandinstrumentation.springeropen.com/> documenting the progress of R&D activities that would allow FCC-ee to meet its target physics goals.

2.1. FCC PHYSICS WORKSHOP IN LIVERPOOL

The FCC physics community gathered online from 7 to 11 February 2022 to reflect the status and achievements of FCC Physics, Experiments, and Detectors studies and initiate new activities.

The 5th FCC Physics Workshop was organized by the University of Liverpool together with CERN. Gathering over 600 participants, the meeting offered an opportunity to sharpen the FCC's physics case. A future electron-positron circular collider (FCC-ee) will deliver record-breaking luminosities to study all standard model particles and their interactions with the Higgs boson – with unprecedented precision. In addition, speakers referred to the physics studies opened by the direct kinematic reach of a proton collider (FCC-hh) hosted in the same tunnel. The staged approach provides the most efficient and pragmatic way towards the energy frontier while the scientific synergies between FCC-ee and FCC-hh give access to a diverse scientific programme that would contribute to answering some of the biggest questions in modern physics.

The workshop covered detector requirements as well as progress on the design of new analysis tools and methods for FCC-ee. The goal, as part of the feasibility study, is to provide a coherent set of solutions to obtain the maximum benefit from the improved statistics, variety of channels, and sensitivity to new physics of the new collider.

The meeting also allowed establishing constructive collaboration with linear collider teams and aligning the R&D plans with other roadmaps and activities at European and global level. In that direction, discussions during the meeting informed the preparation of an FCC paper that will be submitted in the Snowmass process in the US.

The programme and presentations of the 5th FCC Physics Workshop can be found at: <https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/>

2.1.1. List of presentations documenting the experimental physics goals (Physics Workshop in Liverpool)

The 5th FCC Physics, Experiments and Detectors workshop reflects the status and achievements of FCC PED studies and initiate new activities. All PED Working group packages were represented, Physics Programme, Physics Performance, Detector Concepts and Physics Software and Computing, as well as the joint FCC-ee Accelerator-Experiment working groups (machine-detector interface (MDI) and centre-of-mass energy calibration, polarization and monochromatization (EPOL)). Joint sessions and tutorials reinforced the synergies between working groups.

Welcome and overview			
Welcome to the 5th FCC Physics Workshop	Carsten Peter Welsch	Cockcroft Institute / University of Liverpool	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4594206/attachments/2385613/4077219/FCC%20Physics%20Workshop%202022%20-%20Opening.pdf
Welcome and CERN vision	Joachim Josef Mnich	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4594207/attachments/2385499/4077004/JM%20Liverpool.pdf
The FCC feasibility study	Michael Benedikt	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4594213/attachments/2385608/4077362/220207_FCC-FeasibilityStudyStatus.pdf
Recap of the FCC-ee physics potential and open questions	Christophe Grojean	DESY Hamburg and Humboldt University Berlin	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4705772/attachments/2385677/4077366/Grojean_FCce_Liverpool.pdf
Recap of the FCC-hh physics potential and open questions	Monica D'Onofrio	University of Liverpool	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4705775/attachments/2385670/4077305/FCCWorkshop_FCChh_Recap.pdf
Recap of the FCC-eh physics potential and open questions	Daniel Britzger	Max-Planck-Institut für Physik München	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4705778/attachments/2385556/4081457/220207-britzger-FCCeh-week.pdf
PED study introduction and goals of meeting	Patrick Janot	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4594214/attachments/2385558/4077625/Introduction_GoalsOfTheMeeting.pdf
Higgs Physics			
FCC in America and the Snowmass process	Sarah Eno	University of Maryland	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4705874/attachments/2385424/4076879/FCC_USA_snowmass_liverpool_feb2022.pdf
Naturalness	Michael Geller	Tel Aviv University	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4705875/attachments/2385990/4077876/FCC%20Naturalness%202022.pdf

Higgs couplings and naturalness	Ennio Salvioni	Università e INFN, Padova	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4705876/attachments/2385815/4077571/Talk_5th_FCC_Workshop_upload.pdf
Higgs Physics at CEPC	Gang Li	IHEP, CAS	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4705888/attachments/2385840/4077649/cepc_higgs_GangLI.pdf
	Li Gang	IHEP	
Higgs mass and ZH cross-section from Z(mumu)H events	Ang Li	APC, CNRS/IN2P3 and Université de Paris	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4708082/attachments/2385658/4077518/2021_02_07_FCC_WEEK_Ang_LI.pdf
	Jan Eysermans	Massachusetts Institute of Technology	
Higgs to invisible	Andrew Mehta	University of Liverpool	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4708083/attachments/2385645/4077258/mehta.pdf
	Nikolaos Rompotis	University of Liverpool	
Hbb, Hcc, Hgg	Giovanni Marchiori	APC, CNRS/IN2P3 and Université de Paris	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4708094/attachments/2385936/4077774/2022_02_07%20-%20Higgs%20hadronic%20branching%20ratios%20with%20ZllH%20at%20FCCee.pdf
Higgs self-coupling	Roberto Salerno	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4708095/attachments/2385937/4077776/RobertoSalerno_FCC_Liverpool.pdf
Di-higgs studies in the bb-tau channel, and BSM Higgs searches at the FCC-hh,	Matthew James Sullivan	University of Liverpool	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4708096/attachments/2386220/4078318/DiHiggs_bbtautau_FCChh.pdf
Detecting Heavy Higgs Bosons from Natural SUSY at a 100 TeV Hadron Collider	Howard Baer		https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4708097/attachments/2385456/4078261/FCC_SUSYHiggs.pdf
Di-Higgs with missing transverse momentum at FCC-hh	Birgit Sylvia Stapf	Deutsches Elektronen-Synchrotron	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4708098/attachments/2386033/4077952/2022-02-07_FCCWorkshop_DiHiggs_MET_birgit.pdf

Unveiling the Higgs at FCC-hh with new diboson precision measurements	Alejo Nahuel Rossia	University of Manchester	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4708099/attachments/2385583/4077384/Rossia_Vh_FCCws_2022.pdf
Higgs and Electroweak ep Physics at FCC-eh	Christian Schwabenberger	Deutsches Elektronen-Synchrotron	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4710392/attachments/2386393/4078953/FCCeh_EWK_Higgs.pdf
ee -> H	David d'Enterria	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4710393/attachments/2384428/4074759/dde_e_Yukawa_FCC_week_feb22.pdf
Monochromatization	Frank Zimmermann	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4710421/attachments/2386373/4078598/monochromatization%20.pdf
Particle ID with Dual Readout calorimeter	Luca Torresi	INFN - National Institute for Nuclear Physics	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4710394/attachments/2386366/4078587/Particle%20ID%20with%20DRC.pdf

A beam test for the cluster counting technique	Francesco Grancagnolo	Universita & INFN Lecce	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4710395/attachments/2386630/4078968/CluCouFCCWeek2022.pdf
quark/gluon discrimination	Gregory Soyez	IPhT, CEA Saclay	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4710422/attachments/2386664/4079022/lund-qg.pdf
Flavour Tagging with ParticleNet	Loukas Gouskos	CERN, Michele Selvaggi	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4710423/attachments/2386728/4079172/lg_jettagging_fccweek2022.pdf
Strange Jet Tagging at FCCee using CNNs	Eduardo Ploerer	University of Zurich & VUB	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4710424/attachments/2386869/4079308/S-Tagging_CNN_FCCPhysicsWorkshop.pdf
H-> ss	Valentina Cairo	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4710425/attachments/2386849/4079308/S-Tagging_CNN_FCCPhysicsWorkshop.pdf

			079274/StrangeCoupling_FCCWorkshop2022_VMMC AIRO 8Feb2022.pdf
Flavour at FCC			
Z-boson LFV	Xabier Marcano	Universidad Autonoma de Madrid	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4710428/attachments/2386324/4078519/FCCWorkshop_xmarcano.pdf
Tau physics	Alberto Lusiani	Scuola Normale Superiore and INFN, sezione di Pisa	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4710427/attachments/2387021/4081448/alusiani-fcc-feb22.pdf
Probing B-Anomalies via Dimuon Tails at a Future Collider	Sebastian Jaeger	University of Sussex	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4710431/attachments/2387071/4079841/fcc-physics-jaeger.pdf
Discovering true tauonium in two-photon fusion processes at FCC-ee	David d'Enterria	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4710432/attachments/2386374/4081318/dde_ditaonium_FCC_week_feb22.pdf
	Hua-Sheng Shao	Peking University, Beijing, China	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4710434/attachments/2387214/4080086/Talk_FCC.pdf
B to K* tau tau	Tristan Miralles	Université Clermont Auvergne	
Bs to PhiPhi	Roy Aleksan	Université Paris-Saclay	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4710435/attachments/2387236/4080133/Bs-to-phiPhi.pdf
Ks reconstruction and B+ to D K+	Emmanuel Francois Perez	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4710436/attachments/2387129/4079934/2022_02_08_Liverpool_Ksreco.pdf
B to K* nu nu	Matthew Kenzie William	University of Warwick	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4710437/attachments/2386338/4078537/slides.pdf
Detector Concepts			
Noble Liquid Calorimetry for a Future FCC-ee Experiment	Brieuc Francois	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4708987/attachments/2387716/4080914/20220209_Brieuc_Francois_Noble_Liquid_Cal

			orimetry_forFCCee_FCCworkshop2022.pdf
Superconducting Detector Magnets for FCC-ee	Nikkie Deelen	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4708988/attachments/2387817/4081086/fcceeFor%20FCCPhysicsWeek_NDeelen.pdf
The preshower and the muon detection system of the IDEA detector for FCC-ee	Giulio Mezzadri	Università e INFN, Ferrara	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4708989/attachments/2387542/4169295/FCC_Liverpool(1).pdf
Test Beam Results and R&D Programme for a Highly Granular Fibre-Sampling Dual-Readout Calorimeter	Gabriella Gaudio	INFN-Pavia	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4708993/attachments/2387822/4081097/20220208_dualreadout.pdf
CALICE overview	Vincent Boudry	LLR – CNRS, École polytechnique, Institut Polytechnique de Paris	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4708994/attachments/2387923/4081411/2022-02-08_CALICE_for_FCCee.pdf
Semi-Digital Hadronic Calorimeter	Imad Laktineh	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4709000/attachments/2387798/4081064/FCC-2022.pdf
Combining Dual-Readout Crystals and Fibers in a Hybrid Calorimeter for IDEA	Marco Toliman Lucchini	Università & INFN, Milano-Bicocca	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4709001/attachments/2387594/4080760/22_02_09_FCC-PhysicsWorkshop_CombiningDual-ReadoutCrystals_and_Fibers_in_a_HybridCalorimeter.pdf
DMAPS for large area FCC trackers	Attilio Andreazza	Università degli Studi e INFN Milano	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4709002/attachments/2387698/4081415/20220209_CMOSTracker_FCC.pdf
Large area curved silicon modules for future trackers	Adrian Bevan	Queen Mary University of London	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4709005/attachments/2387601/4080788/2022-Feb-FCC-ZMD.pdf
A Triplet Track Trigger for FCC-hh & its impact on	Tamasi Kar	Ruprecht Karls Universität Heidelberg	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4709010/attachments/2387936/4

measuring the Higgs self-coupling			081953/TKar_FCCPhyWeek2022.pdf
FCC Physics: QCD			
Hadronization corrections in event shapes	Silvia Ferrario Ravasio	University of Milan - Bicocca & University of Oxford	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4709014/attachments/2387668/4080820/2022_02_09_Fcc.pdf
Jet energy spectrum and substructure in e^+e^- collisions at 91.2 GeV	Yen-Jie Lee	Massachusetts Institute of Technology	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4709013/attachments/2387690/4082072/20220109-ALEPH-FCCworkshop_yenje_v5.pdf
Event Generators & Parton Showers	Simon Platzer	University of Graz & DESY	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4709011/attachments/2388114/4081683/slides-reduced.pdf
Parton structure, forward physics and eA and FCC-eh	Krzysztof Piotrkowski	AGH UST Krakow	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4710476/attachments/2388129/4084401/fcc-eh_KPv2.pdf
FCC Physics: Precision Electroweak			
KKMCee status and planning	Staszek Jadach	Polish Academy of Sciences	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4709027/attachments/2387608/4082359/2022-02-09-FCC-Physics.pdf
Path to FCC-ee 0.01% Theoretical Luminosity Precision	Bennie Ward	Baylor University	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4719613/attachments/2387802/4083881/ward-lumi-fcc2022.pdf
Three-loop elliptic integrals for the Standard Model rho parameter	Samuel Abreu	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4709022/attachments/2388218/4082116/fcc_2022.pdf
Electroweak pseudo-observables and Z-boson form factors at two-loop accuracy	Johann Usovitsch	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4709023/attachments/2388154/4082528/Usovitsch.pdf
Partonic structure of electron	Stefano Frixione	INFN, Stefano Frixione	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4709025/attachments/2388428/4082276/eepdf.FCC.pdf

Tools for higher loops	Janusz Gluza	University of Silesia	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4709026/attachments/2387808/4081990/FCC_Liverpool_2022.pdf
Path to precision	Ayres Freitas		https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4709021/attachments/2387672/4080835/talk.pdf
Machine Detector Interface			
FCC-eh accelerator / IR and common hh detector	Kevin Daniel Joel Andre	University of Liverpool	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4708159/attachments/2388496/4083028/FCCweek2022%20-%20FCC-eh%20.pdf
IP generated radiation monitor for center-of-mass energy measurements	Andrea Ciarma	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4708160/attachments/2388702/4082929/FCCee_IR_radiation_monitor_Ciarma.pdf
Low angle luminosity monitoring	Helmut Burkhardt	Albert Ludwigs Universitaet Freiburg	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4708161/attachments/2388441/4083015/Low_Angle_Bhabha_2022_02_10.pdf
MDI design integration	Luigi Pellegrino		https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4708162/attachments/2388566/4083416/5th%20FCC%20Physics%20workshop-MDI%20design%20integration-%20Pellegrino.pdf
The quadrupole QD0 for the SuperB interaction region	Stefania Farinon	INFN e Universita Genova	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4708163/attachments/2388737/4083040/farinon-QD0_rev3.pdf
Status of beam backgrounds in Belle II at SuperKEKB	Andrii Natochii	University of Hawaii at Manoa	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4708164/attachments/2388621/4082777/FCC_workshop_2022_NATOCII_v2.pdf
Software			
Status of the software	Gerardo Ganis		https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4708165/attachments/2388903/4083373/FCC-SnC-Status-10Feb2022.pdf

Lesson learned when migrating the IDEA drift chamber software to EDM4hep	Lia Lavezzi	Università e INFN Torino	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4708166/attachments/2388798/4083172/20220210_edm4hep_lavezzi.pdf
Lesson learned when migrating the IDEA DR calo software to DD4hep and to EDM4hep	Iacopo Vivarelli	University of Sussex	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4708178/attachments/2388654/4082828/220210_shKo_FCC_workshop.pdf
	Roberto Ferrari	INFN Pavia	
	Sang Hyun Ko	Seoul National University	
FCC software step-by-step	Valentin Volk	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4708179/attachments/2388908/4083386/fccsw-step-by-step.pdf
FCC Physics: Direct BSM searches			
Discovery stories	Tiann Tevong You	Imperial College London	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4708151/attachments/2389006/4083598/2022_02%20-%20Liverpool%20-%20FCC%20workshop%20-%20Discovery%20Stories.pdf
High-dimensional Anomaly Detection with Radiative Return in e^+e^- Collisions	Julia Lynne Gonski	Columbia University	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4708150/attachments/2388612/4083653/0210_jgonski_fcc_eanomdet.pdf
Long-Lived Particles	Juliette Alimena	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4708153/attachments/2388886/4083318/FCCLLP_FCCWorkshop_10Feb2022.pdf
Light BSM scalars at e^+e^- machines	Tania Natalie Robens		https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4708154/attachments/2388112/4081681/robens_fcc.pdf
Tera-Zooming in on light (composite) axion-like particles	Giacomo Cacciapaglia		https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4708156/attachments/2389082/4083713/Cacciapaglia_TeraZooming.pdf
BSM & top Physics with FCC-eh	Oliver Fischer		https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4708157/attachments/2388995/4084158/FCC22_Fischer_Top_BSM.pdf

FCC Physics: Neutrinos and Flavour			
Majorana vs Dirac Heavy Neutral Leptons	Richard Ruiz	Institute of Nuclear Physics (IFJ) PAN	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/472131/attachments/2389563/4084650/r Ruiz FCC5 Dirac Majorana.pdf
Flavour at FCC	Jernej F. Kamenik		https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/472138/attachments/2389479/4084661/Kamenik FCC-ee Flavour 2022.pdf
Joint Software, Physics Performance and Detector session			
Overview of FCCSW and Key4HEP	Clement Helsens	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4712000/attachments/2389695/4084912/Helsens-FCCPhysicsWS-02-2022.pdf
Status of CLD Software	Andre Sailer	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4712001/attachments/2389464/4085075/220211 FCCee CLD_sailer.pdf
Status of IDEA software	Walaa Elmetenawee	Universita e INFN, Bari	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4712002/attachments/2389585/4084981/IDEA_Walaa.pdf
Status of the FCC-ee LAr calorimeter software	Brieuc Francois	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4712003/attachments/2389721/4084969/20220211_Brieuc_Francois_LAr_Software_FC_Cworkshop2022.pdf
Next steps			
ECM calibration and Polarization status and plans	Alain Blondel	Universite de Geneve	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4708125/attachments/2389519/4085352/20220211_Keintzel_FCCPhysicsWorkshop2022.pdf
	Jacqueline Keintzel	CERN	
Electroweak precision measurements status	Juan Alcaraz Maestre	Centro de Investigaciones Energéticas, Medioambientales y Tecnológicas CIEMAT, Madrid	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4708127/attachments/2389843/4085230/Alcaraz_FCCPhysicsWorkshop_EW_11Feb2022.pdf

MDI status and plans	Manuela Boscolo	INFN e Laboratori Nazionali di Frascati	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4708128/attachments/2389848/4085235/MDI_Status_Plans_mboscolo.pdf
Mandate for the Software and Computing Team	David Lange	Princeton University	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4708135/attachments/2389973/4085450/fcc_220209.pdf
Physics performance plans	Emmanuel Francois Perez	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4708137/attachments/2389970/4085445/PPe-FCCWS-Feb2022.pdf
	Patrizia Azzi	INFN Padova	
	Frank Simon	Max-Planck-Institut fuer Physik	
Physics Programme plans	Matthew Mccullough Philip	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4708140/attachments/2389980/4085890/PhysicsProgram_Plans.pdf
Detector concepts plans	Mogens Dam	University of Copenhagen	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1066234/contributions/4708142/attachments/2389903/4085334/20220211-FCCWorkshop-DetConcepts.pdf

2.1.2. List of presentations documenting the experimental physics goals (FCC Week 2022)

FCC-ee: Physics of Precision and Discovery	Janusz Gluza (University of Silesia (PL))	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1064327/contributions/4893179/attachments/2453027/4204020/FCC_Week_Paris_2022.pdf
EW & Precision: Performance	Christoph Paus (Massachusetts Inst. of Technology (US))	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1064327/contributions/4893189/attachments/2453277/4204169/fcc-week-paris.pdf
Flavours: Programme	Jernej Fasel Kamenik (Jozef Stefan Institute (SI))	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1064327/contributions/4893190/attachments/2453147/4203917/Kamenik_FCC-Week_Flavours.pdf
Flavours Performance	Stephane Monteil (LP Clermont)	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1064327/contributions/4893191/attachments/2453359/4204363/Flavours_FCC_Paris_20220531.pdf
High- precision QCD physics at FCC-ee	David d'Enterria (CERN)	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1064327/contributions/4888547/attachments/2453143/4207173/dde_QCD_FCCee_FCCweek_Paris_may22.pdf
Top: Programme Performance	Philipp Roloff (CERN)	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1064327/contributions/4893195/attachments/2453068/4203779/fcc-week_2022_roloff.pdf
Higgs: Programme	Gauthier Durieux (CERN)	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1064327/contributions/4893196/attachments/2453281/4204174/durieux-fccweek-31may2022.pdf
Higgs: Performance	Jan Eysermans (Massachusetts Inst. of Technology (US))	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1064327/contributions/4893198/attachments/2453156/4204178/Higgs_Performance_FCCWeek_May2022.pdf
FCC BSM Physics programme: theory overview	Tevong You (University of Cambridge)	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1064327/contributions/4893175/attachments/2453296/4204206/2022_05%20-%20FCC%20Week%20-%20BSM%20physics%20programme.pdf
BSM Review and Plans	Rebeca Gonzalez Suarez (Uppsala University (SE))	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1064327/contributions/4888546/attachments/2453459/4204589/FCC-week-2022.pdf

Long lived particles at FCC	Suchita Kulkarni (University of Graz)	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1064327/contributions/4893178/attachments/2453421/4204743/Kulkarni_FCC_week_2022.pdf
Search for Long-Lived Particles at the Future FCC-ee	Juliette Alimena (CERN)	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1064327/contributions/4888544/attachments/2453435/4204538/FCC_LL_PCCWeek_31May2022.pdf
Detector Concepts Overview	Mogens Dam (University of Copenhagen (DK))	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1064327/contributions/4893208/attachments/2454038/4214309/20220601-Paris-DetectorConcepts.pdf
The CLD Detector Concept	Andre Sailer (CERN)	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1064327/contributions/4893180/attachments/2452299/4204992/220601_FCCWeek_CLD_sailer.pdf
The IDEA detector concept	Paolo Giacomelli (Universita e INFN, Bologna (IT))	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1064327/contributions/4888532/attachments/2453905/4205914/IDEA_detector-concept-FCC-week-2022.pdf
LAr based detector concept	Martin Aleksa (CERN)	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1064327/contributions/4893219/attachments/2454064/4206036/FCC-ee-Experiment-Layouts-20220601.pdf
Summaries on physics, experiments and detectors	Patrick Janot (CERN)	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1064327/contributions/4893356/attachments/2455654/4208921/PED_Summary2022.pdf

2.1.3. FCC France – Italy dedicated workshop

The first joint FCC-France & Italy workshop covering all experimental aspects of the FCC-ee programme (i.e. Higgs, Top, EW, HF and SM physics) took place at the Institut de Physique des 2 Infinis de Lyon (IP2I Lyon) from 21 to 23 November 2022. The workshop was hosted at the Université Claude Bernard Lyon 1 Campus, Domaine Scientifique de la Doua, Villeurbanne (next to Lyon).

This meeting also corresponds to the 4th FCC-France / Higgs, Top & ElectroWeak Factory workshop. Its goal was to intensify French and Italian collaboration and participation in the FCC feasibility study through accelerator and detector concepts studies, concrete studies on physics and the constraints that this physics entails on detectors, in particular the physics of FCC-ee, but also FCC-hh. Detector R&D, Progress on Theory and on Accelerators for FCC were presented in detail. Synergies with developments for linear colliders were also discussed helping to identify common R&D areas on detector technologies.

The presentations capturing the experimental goals of the FCC-ee programme are available as presentations on Indico: <https://indico.in2p3.fr/event/27968/timetable/#20221121>

2.2. FCC PUBLICATIONS

2.2.1. EPJ Plus focus point on a future electroweak factory

The focus issue of EPJ+, published together with Spring/Nature and using the tools provided by Overleaf, forms a precious reference document to evaluate the progress toward the realisation of FCCs. Following the submission of M5.1, 12 more essays were published OA format and represented the challenges and opportunities that a project like FCC offers could inform a wider community of scientists and engineers working on similar topics and inform potential partners from academia and research centres.

As described in the EPJ Plus website: “The aims of this peer-reviewed online journal are to distribute and archive all relevant material required to document, assess, validate and reconstruct in detail the body of knowledge in the physical and related sciences.” The scope of the EPJ Plus, encompassing a broad landscape of fields and disciplines in the physical and related sciences and the peer-review process adhering to high-quality standards about the quality and thoroughness of presentation made EPJ Plus a suitable publication platform for these essays covering a wide range of topics including detector technologies, accelerator physics, theoretical physics and computational & software challenges. Furthermore, the high impact factor of EPJ Plus, scoring 3.911 in 2020, demonstrates the journal’s influence and visibility in the community.

The essays were written and edited using the EPJ+ Overleaf templates developed by the FCCIS WP5 project beneficiaries, while the peer reviewed process was supervised by a dedicated team of Guest Editors acting in addition and in coordination with the journal’s Editorial Board. In identifying the Guest Editors, beyond their knowledge and expertise in relevant fields, we strived for a gender (achieving a 50%-50% balance between male & female editors) and geographical balance.

The Guest Editors for this special volume are:

PART I

1. Andrei Seryi (Director of Accelerator Division at Jefferson Lab, USA)
2. Anke-Susanne Müller (Director of the Karlsruhe Institute for Beam Physics and Technology IBPT, Germany)

PART II

1. Beate Heinemann (Director of Research at DESY & Professor Albert-Ludwigs-Universität Freiburg, Germany)
2. Patrick Koppenburg (Research Physicist at Nikhef, The Netherlands)

Part III

1. Pilar Hernandez (University of Valencia, IFC, Spain)
2. Matthew McCullough (CERN, Switzerland)

PART IV

1. Gloria CORTI (CERN, Geneva)
2. Junichi TANAKA (Professor at University of Tokyo, Japan)

2.2.2. Table of published OA papers in EPJ Plus (during 2022) capturing the research opportunities at FCCs

The table below details the published papers and provides the DOI numbers for retrieving the Open Access published version. Publications are classified based on the following indexes:

- Article in Journal (=1)
- Publication in Conference proceedings/Workshop (=2)
- Book/Monograph (=3)

- Chapter in Book (=4)
- Thesis/Dissertation, Other (=5)

Is this publication available in Open-Access, or will it be made available?

- Yes: Green Open Access
- Yes: Gold Open Access
- No

Type	Title	Authors	Title of the Journal/ Proc./Book	Is Peer-reviewed (Y/N)	Is open Access (Yes: Green, Gold ; No)	Is a joint public/private publication (Y/N)	DOI
1	Key4hep, a framework for future HEP experiments and its use in FCC	Gerardo Ganis, Clément Helsens, Valentin Völkl	EPJ Plus	YES	YES, Gold	NO	10.1140/epjp/s13360-021-02213-1
1	Offline computing resources for FCC-ee and related challenges	Clément Helsens & Gerardo Ganis	EPJ Plus	YES	YES, Gold	NO	10.1140/epjp/s13360-021-02189-y
1	Review and outlook of accelerator-related codes and their interplay with the experiments software	Manuela Boscolo, Helmut Burkhardt, Gerardo Ganis & Clément Helsens	EPJ Plus	YES	YES, Gold	NO	10.1140/epjp/s13360-021-02212-2
1	IR challenges and the machine detector interface at FCC-ee	Manuela Boscolo, Helmut Burkhardt, Katsunobu Oide & Michael K. Sullivan	EPJ Plus	YES	YES, Gold	NO	10.1140/epjp/s13360-021-02031-5
1	How to increase the physics output	D. Shatilov	EPJ Plus	YES	YES, Gold	NO	10.1140/epjp/s13360-

	per MW.h for FCC-ee?						022-02346-x
1	RF system challenges for future e^+e^- circular colliders	Olivier Brunner, Erk Jensen, Ivan Karpov, Eric Montesinos, Franck Peauger & Igor Syrathev	EPJ Plus	YES	YES, Gold	NO	10.1140/epjp/s13360-021-02228-8
1	The challenge of monochromatization on Direct s-channel Higgs production channel	Angeles Faus-Golfe, Marco Alan Valdivia Garcia & Frank Zimmermann	EPJ Plus	YES	YES, Gold	NO	10.1140/epjp/s13360-021-02151-y
1	FCC Physics Motivation	Christophe Grojean	EPJ Plus	YES	YES, Gold	NO	https://doi.org/10.1140/epjp/s13360-021-01848-4
1	Tracking and vertex detectors at FCC-ee	Nicola Bacchetta, Paula Collins & Petra Riedler	EPJ Plus	YES	YES, Gold	NO	10.1140/epjp/s13360-021-02323-w
1	Measuring the electron Yukawa coupling via resonant s-channel Higgs production at FCC-ee	David d'Enterria, Andres Poldaru & George Wojcik	EPJ Plus	YES	YES, Gold	NO	10.1140/epjp/s13360-021-02204-2
1	FCC-ee overview: new opportunities create new challenges	Alain Blondel, Patrick Janot	EPJ Plus	YES	YES, Gold	NO	10.1140/epjp/s13360-021-02154-9

1	Higgs and top physics reconstruction challenges and opportunities at FCC-ee	Patrizia Azzi, Loukas Gouskos, Michele Selvaggi & Frank Simon	EPJ Plus	YES	YES, Gold	NO	10.1140/epjp/s13360-021-02223-z
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Finally, it should also be noted that beyond the collaboration with Springer/Nature, dedicated communities have been set up in Zenodo for Open Access publishing the work carried out in the framework of the FCC Feasibility Study.

These communities can be found here: <https://zenodo.org/communities/?p=FCC>

2.2.3. Table of published OA papers in EPJ Techniques and Instrumentation capturing the research opportunities at FCCs

EPJ Techniques and Instrumentation is a Springer/Nature journal primarily focusing on the design, implementation, and application of new techniques in all areas of the physical and applied sciences.

Of particular interest to the journal are advances produced by:

- Laboratory-specific custom instrumentation and diagnostics
- Innovative and clever experimental techniques
- Refinements to established experimental setups
- Novel analytical methods

Such articles should summarize a novel, significant result, and provide a detailed description of the equipment, methods, or techniques used to produce the result. They may also include discussions of underlying theory, and/or potential cross-disciplinary applications.

In 2022, a special collection “Accelerating the design of the future circular collider” was launched to document progress on the Future Circular Collider (FCC) lepton (electron-positron) design that inform the experimental goals and physics potential of the proposed collider.

During the feasibility study, the parameters of the rings are in flux, but this collection of articles provide updates to the concepts put forth in the Conceptual Design Report. Topics include a parameter and layout update for the electron-positron collider, optics considerations for the hadron collider, fundamental beam physics challenges including collective effects as well as optics correction and stabilization, and possible technological solutions for some of the challenging hardware in the FCC complex.

The guest editors for this volume are: Angeles Faus-Golfe, CNRS/In2p3 and Tor Raubenheimer, SLAC.

The papers published in 2022 in Open Access are:

Type	Title	Authors	Title of the Journal/ Proc./Book	Is Peer-reviewed (Y/N)	Is open Access (Yes: Green, Gold ; No)	Is a joint public/private publication (Y/N)	DOI / Indico /Link to the publication
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1	The FCC-ee vacuum system, from conceptual to prototyping	Roberto Kersevan	EPJ Techniques and Instrumentation	YES	YES	NO	10.1140/epjti/s40485-022-00087-w
1	Impedance modelling and collective effects in the Future Circular e^+e^- Collider with 4 Experimental Points (IPs)	M. Migliorati, C. Antuono, E. Carideo, Y. Zhang and M. Zobov	EPJ Techniques and Instrumentation	YES	YES	NO	10.1140/epjti/s40485-022-00084-z
1	Mitigation of electron cloud effects in the FCC-ee collider	Fatih Yaman, Giovanni Iadarola, Roberto Kersevan, Salim Ogur, Kazuhito Ohmi, Frank Zimmermann and Mikhail Zobov	EPJ Techniques and Instrumentation	YES	YES	NO	10.1140/epjti/s40485-022-00085-y
1	Considerations on combined-function optics for high-energy storage rings and colliders	Massimo Giovannozzi	EPJ Techniques and Instrumentation	YES	YES	NO	10.1140/epjti/s40485-022-00085-y
1	A semi-passive beam dilution system for the FCC-ee collider	Alexander Krainer, Wolfgang Bartmann, Marco Calviani, Yann Dutheil, Anton Lechner, Antonio Perillo Marcone, Salim Ogur &	EPJ Techniques and Instrumentation	YES	YES	NO	10.1140/epjti/s40485-022-00078-x

		Rebecca Ramjiawan					
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2.2.4. Table of published OA proceedings from international conferences covering the physics opportunities of the FCC-ee

Further to the above-listed papers, several other publications cover the experimental physics goals of FCC-ee including detector and accelerator design parameters. A number of papers - listed in the table below - were presented during the [International Conference in High-Energy Physics \(ICHEP\) 2022](#) conference as well as in [International Particle Accelerator Conference \(IPAC\) 2022](#); two of the most prestigious conferences for the global particle physics community. The table also lists to papers published in Physical Review Accelerators and Beams.

Type	Title	Authors	Title of the Journal/ Proc./Book	Is Peer-reviewed	Is open Access (Yes: Green, Gold; No)	Is a joint public/private publication	DOI / Indico /Link to the publication
2	Status of detector requirements for FCC-ee	Marina Cobal (Udine U. and INFN, Udine)	Proceedings of Science	NO	YES	NO	10.22323/1.414.0353
2	Status of the High Energy Booster of the lepton option of the future circular collider	B. Dalena (IRFU, Saclay), A. Chance (IRFU, Saclay), F. Antoniou (CERN), O. Etisken (Bogazici U), A. Mashal (IPM, Tehran), T. Raubenheimer (SLAC), M. Zampetakis (CERN), F. Zimmermann (CERN)	Proceedings of Science	NO	YES	NO	10.22323/1.414.0042
2	Jet-Flavour Tagging at FCC-ee	Kunal Gautam (Vrije U., Brussels and Brussels U., IIHE and Zurich U.)	Proceedings of Science	NO	YES	NO	10.22323/1.414.1147

2	High-precision QCD physics at FCC-ee	Francesco Giuli (CERN)	Proceedings of Science	NO	YES	NO	10.22323/1.414.0820
2	First Optics Design for a Transverse Monochromatic Scheme for the Direct S-Channel Higgs Production at FCC-ee Collider	Hongping Jiang (Harbin Inst. Tech. and IJCLab, Orsay), Angeles Faus-Golfe (IJCLab, Orsay), Katsunobu Oide (KEK, Tsukuba), Zhandong Zhang (Beijing, Inst. High Energy Phys. and IJCLab, Orsay), Frank Zimmermann (CERN)	Journals of Accelerator Conferences (JACOW)	NO	YES	NO	10.18429/JACoW-IPAC2022-WEPOPT017
2	HOM Coupler Design and Optimization for the FCC-ee W Working Point	Sosoho-Abasi Udongwo (U. Rostock), Rama Calaga (CERN), Shahnam Gorgi Zadeh (CERN), Ursula van Rienen (U. Rostock)	Journals of Accelerator Conferences (JACOW)	NO	YES	NO	10.18429/JACoW-IPAC2022-TUPOTK015
2	Studies and Mitigation of Collective Effects in FCC-ee	Mauro Migliorati (U. Rome La Sapienza (main) and INFN, Rome), Chiara Antuono (CERN and U. Rome La Sapienza (main)), Mostafa Behtouei	Journals of Accelerator Conferences (JACOW)	NO	YES	NO	10.18429/JACoW-IPAC2022-WEOXGD1

		(Frascati), Emanuela Carideo (CERN and U. Rome La Sapienza (main) and INFN, Rome), Bruno Spataro (Frascati), Yuan Zhang(Beijing , Inst. High Energy Phys.), Mikhail Zobov (Frascati)					
2	Prospects for Optics Measurements in FCC-ee	Jacqueline Keintzel (CERN), Rogelio Tomás García (CERN), Frank Zimmermann (CERN)	Journals of Accelerator Conferences (JACOW)	NO	YES	NO	10.18429/J ACoW- IPAC2022- TUOZSP1
2	Concepts and Considerations for FCC-ee Top-Up Injection Strategies	Rebecca Ramjiawan (CERN), Masamitsu Aiba (PSI, Villigen), Wolfgang Bartmann (CERN), Yann Duheil (CERN), Michael Hofer (CERN)	Journals of Accelerator Conferences (JACOW)	NO	YES	NO	10.18429/J ACoW- IPAC2022- WEPOTK 025
2	Centre-of-Mass Energy in FCC-ee	Jacqueline Keintzel (CERN), Alain Blondel (CERN), Dmitry Shatilov (CERN), Rogelio Tomás García (CERN), Frank Zimmermann (CERN)	Journals of Accelerator Conferences (JACOW)	NO	YES	NO	10.18429/J ACoW- IPAC2022- WEPOST0 07

2	Development of Collimation Simulations for the FCC-ee	Andrey Abramov (CERN), Roderik Bruce (CERN), Felix Carlier (Ecole Polytechnique, Lausanne), Michael Hofer (CERN), Giovanni Iadarola (CERN), Laurence Nevay (JAI, UK), Tatiana Pieloni (Ecole Polytechnique, Lausanne), Milica Rakic (Ecole Polytechnique, Lausanne), Stefano Redaelli (CERN), Simon White (ESRF, Grenoble)	Journals of Accelerator Conferences (JACOW)	NO	YES	NO	10.18429/JACoW-IPAC2022-WEPOST016
2	Studies on Top-Up Injection into the FCC-ee Collider Ring	Patrick Hunchak (Saskatchewan U., CLS and Saskatchewan U.), Masamitsu Aiba (PSI, Villigen), Wolfgang Bartmann (CERN), Mark Boland (Saskatchewan U., CLS and Saskatchewan U.), Yann Dutheil (CERN), Michael Hofer (CERN), Rebecca Ramjiawan (CERN), Frank Zimmermann (CERN)	Journals of Accelerator Conferences (JACOW)	NO	YES	NO	10.18429/JACoW-IPAC2022-WEPOST011

2	Development of an Electro-Optical Longitudinal Bunch Profile Monitor at KARA Towards a Beam Diagnostics Tool for FCC-ee	Micha Reißig (KIT, Karlsruhe), Miriam Brosi (KIT, Karlsruhe), Erik Bründermann (KIT, Karlsruhe), Stefan Funkner (KIT, Karlsruhe), Bastian Härer (KIT, Karlsruhe), Anke-Susanne Müller (KIT, Karlsruhe), Gudrun Niehues (KIT, Karlsruhe), Meghana Patil (KIT, Karlsruhe), Robert Ruprecht (KIT, Karlsruhe), Christina Widmann (KIT, Karlsruhe)	Journals of Accelerator Conferences (JACOW)	NO	YES	NO	\
2	Synchrotron Radiation Impact on the FCC-ee Arcs	Barbara Humann (TU Vienna and CERN), Francesco Cerutti (CERN), Roberto Kersevan (CERN)	Journals of Accelerator Conferences (JACOW)	NO	YES	NO	10.18429/JACoW-IPAC2022-WEPOST02
2	Modelling FCC-ee Using MADX	Léon van Riesen-Haupt (CERN), Helmut Burkhardt (CERN), Tobias Persson (CERN), Rogelio Tomás García (CERN)	Journals of Accelerator Conferences (JACOW)	NO	YES	NO	10.18429/JACoW-IPAC2022-WEPOPT011

2	Design of a Collimation Section for the FCC-ee	Michael Hofer (CERN), Andrey Abramov (CERN), Roderik Bruce (CERN), Maitreyee Moudgalya (Ecole Polytechnique, Lausanne), Katsunobu Oide (CERN), Tatiana Pieloni (Ecole Polytechnique, Lausanne), Frank Zimmermann (CERN)	Journals of Accelerator Conferences (JACOW)	NO	YES	NO	10.18429/JACoW-IPAC2022-WEPOST017
2	Target Studies for the FCC-ee Positron Source	F. Alharthi (IJCLab, Orsay), L. Bandiera (INFN, Ferrara and Ferrara U.), I. Chaikovska (IJCLab, Orsay), R. Chehab (IJCLab, Orsay), J. Diefenbach (Helmholtz Inst., Mainz), O. Khomyshyn (Taras Shevchenko U.), D. Klekots (Taras Shevchenko U.), W. Lauth (Helmholtz Inst., Mainz), A. Mazzolari (INFN, Ferrara and Ferrara U.), V. Mytrochenko (Kharkov, KIPT), S. Ogur (IJCLab, Orsay), M.	Journals of Accelerator Conferences (JACOW)	NO	YES	NO	10.18429/JACoW-IPAC2022-WEPOPT054

		Romagnoni (INFN, Ferrara and Ferrara U.), P. Sievers (CERN), M. Soldani (INFN, Ferrara and Ferrara U.), A.I. Sytov (INFN, Ferrara and Ferrara U.), A. Ushakov (IJCLab, Orsay), S. Wallon (IJCLab, Orsay), Y. Zhao (CERN)					
2	Electron Cloud Build-Up for the Arc Sextupole Sections of the FCC-ee	Jaime Eduardo Rocha Muñoz (Guanajuato U.), Karla Cantún-Ávila (Yucatan Autonoma U.), Geoffrey Maury Cuna (Guanajuato U.), Frank Zimmermann (CERN)	Journals of Accelerator Conferences (JACOW)	NO	YES	NO	10.18429/JACoW-IPAC2022-MOPOST049
2	Status and challenges of the Future Circular Hadron Collider FCC-hh	M. Benedikt (CERN), A. Chance (IRFU, Saclay), B. Dalena (IRFU, Saclay), D. Denisov (Brookhaven), M. Giovannozzi (CERN), J. Gutleber (CERN), R. Losito (CERN), M. Mangano (CERN), T. Raubenheimer (SLAC), W.	Proceedings of Science	NO	YES	NO	10.22323/1.414.0058

		Riegler (CERN), T. Risselada (CERN), D. Schulte (CERN), F. Zimmermann (CERN)					
1	Future Circular Collider: Integrated Programme and Feasibility Study	Michael Benedikt (CERN), Frank Zimmermann (CERN)	Front.in Phys. 10	NO	YES	NO	10.3389/fphy.2022.888078
1	Photostimulated desorption performance of the future circular hadron collider beam screen	L. A. González, V. Baglin, P. Chiggiato, C. Garion, R. Kersevan, S. Casalbuoni, A. Grau, D. Saez de Jauregui, I. Bellafont, and F. Pérez	Phys. Rev. Accel. Beams 24	YES	YES	NO	10.1103/PhysRevAccelBeams.24.113201
1	Self-consistent simulations of beam-beam interaction in future e^+e^- circular colliders including beamstrahlung and longitudinal coupling impedance	Yuan Zhang, Na Wang, Chuntao Lin, Dou Wang, Chenghui Yu, Kazuhito Ohmi, and Mikhail Zobov	Phys. Rev. Accel. Beams 23	YES	YES	NO	10.1103/PhysRevAccelBeams.23.104402

3. USER COMMUNITY SURVEY ON RESEARCH PRIORITIES LAUNCHED

There is consensus that large-scale scientific infrastructures are best built and operated in a sustainable manner as a worldwide joint effort. Community building around the proposed collider-based research infrastructure can be formed through an international, two-way and integrative process, while being geographically balanced and topically complementary. Increasing global collaboration is a prerequisite for success and links with science, research & development and high-tech industry will be essential to further advance and prepare the implementation of the FCC.

In view of this fact, the FCC Feasibility Study has established the FCC Global Collaboration (FGC) Working Group with a clear mandate to engage with countries with mature communities, a long-standing participation in CERN's programmes and the potential to contribute substantially to the Organization's long-term scientific objectives, to facilitate opportunities for national participation in the FCC Feasibility Study. The work of this group is complemented and supported by the Informal Forum of the National Contacts (IFNC) that works to communicate the key goals of the FCC Physics Experiments & Detector (PED) studies and to establish contacts, thus helping to reach a much larger consensus on the future machine, namely FCC-ee (followed by FCC-hh).

An ambitious FCC project requires global collaboration and a long-term commitment to the construction and operations by all parties. The FGC Working Group and the IFNC, supported, by the H2020 FCCIS projects, have implemented during this reporting period a series of meetings with the physics communities and related stakeholders (i.e., funding agencies, national laboratories, research centres and universities) to map the current level of interest on the different research areas offered by the study. These activities initiate discussions with potential major partners as part of the feasibility study and survey current research interests and level of expertise, as well as develop scenarios for future collaborations on ongoing R&D activities, with a focus on the field of physics and on the development of the design and technologies for the accelerator and detector.

A second online survey has been prepared and will be run during 2023, allowing us to understand the key areas of interest within FCC-ee physics as well as current collaborative potential in the R&D activities run in the framework of FCC feasibility study (see Annex).

3.1. FCC-PED INFORMAL FORUM OF NATIONAL CONTACTS

Besides the FCC Global Collaboration Working group (FGC), which engages with countries with recognized participation in CERN's programme to understand opportunities for national participation and eventually set up long-term bilateral or multilateral agreements, the Informal Forum of the National Contacts (IFNC) allows for exchanges between physicists of the different countries, to develop collaborations inside FCC and to help reach the largest consensus on the future machine, namely FCC-ee, followed by FCC-hh.

Every interested country for this approach (currently about 35) has one or two national contacts and has the opportunity to regularly report (every 3-6 months) inside the IFNC meetings, on the development of the FCC activity in his country.

Four broad categories of engagement have been informally defined across different countries: 1. FCC-ee effort well started and well supported; 2. FCC-ee effort getting organized; 3. No FCC-ee effort started, but supporting FCC; 4. Priority FCC/ILC or FCC-es vs. hh unclear; The goal of the forum, with the support of the FCCIS project, is to have eventually all countries converging on category 1.

The conveners of this informal forum are Gregorio Bernardi (IN2P3, France), Tadeusz Lesiak (IFJ PAN, Poland) and Marcin Chruszcz (IFJ PAN, Poland). A number of National meetings have been organized and

were reported in M5.1 “Research Opportunities Captured”). Following the establishment of contacts, a survey has been launched in line with what is foreseen for this milestone of FCCIS.

3.1.1. Table of publications

A key parameter in assessing the experimental physics programme of the proposed FCC-ee is the precision determination of the centre-of-mass energies. Specifically, one of the cornerstones of the physics program lies in the precise (ppm) measurements of the W and Z masses and widths, as well as forward-backward asymmetries. To this effect the centre-of-mass energy distribution should be determined with high precision.

To address this challenge, the FCC technical and financial feasibility study comprises a work package (EPOL) on precision determination of the centre-of-mass energy at FCCee. Ongoing work is based on measuring with unprecedented precision the beam energies that are then converted in centre-of-mass energy and boost using physics events in the detectors, from which the centre-of-mass energy spreads and the beam energy losses around the ring can also be constrained. Additional beam diagnostics have been identified, offering the greatest possible precision, in particular to control the offset and dispersion at the collision points.

These topics were extensively discussed during the second FCC Energy Calibration, Polarization and Monochromatization (EPOL), a dedicated meeting bringing together accelerator and detector experts to review progress and set the next steps for the working groups. Synergies with the US-based Electron Ion Collider (EIC) project were also discussed during the meeting. The meeting also offered the opportunity to discuss similar challenges in the Super-KEKb (Japan) collider as well as in the design of the International Linear Collider (ILC) project.

The key subjects of this workshop are summarized as follows:

- 1) Polarization simulations and spin-tune to beam energy relationship, wigglers and kickers
- 2) Simulation of the relationship between average beam energy and centre-of-mass energies
- 3) Polarimeter design, performance and integration
- 4) Measurements in particle physics experiments
- 5) Monochromatization

The topics discussed and the presentations are available online on Indico as Green Open Access publications: <https://indico.cern.ch/event/1181966/timetable/>. An indicative (i.e., non-exhaustive) list of topics/presentations is given below:

Title	Speaker	Indico Link
Polarization status FCC-ee	Jacqueline Keintzel (CERN)	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1181966/contributions/5041333/attachments/2511007/4315854/20220919_Keintzel_EPOLWS_Status.pdf
Motivation for precision measurements	Christophe Grojean (DESY (Hamburg) and Humboldt University (Berlin))	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1181966/contributions/5041428/attachments/2511859/4317735/Grojean_EPOL_2022_09_20.pdf

Polarized beams proposal for SuperKEKB	Michael Roney	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1181966/contributions/5041429/attachments/2511837/4317681/ChiralBelle-EPOL2022Sept20.pdf
Physics with polarized beams at the EIC	Vadim Ptitsyn	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1181966/contributions/5041430/attachments/2511783/4317563/EIC_Polarized_Beams_VP.pdf
Physics and operational requirements for monochromatization	David d'Enterria (CERN)	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1181966/contributions/5055183/attachments/2512046/4318104/dde_e_Yukawa_EPOLworkshop_sept22.pdf
Measurement of monochromatization parameters	Alain Blondel (Universite de Geneve (CH)), Patrick Janot (CERN)	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1181966/contributions/5055187/attachments/2512271/4318495/EPOL-WG5-AB-measurement%20of%20monochromatization-2022-09-20.pdf
Requirements for polarization measurements	Guy Wilkinson (University of Oxford (GB))	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1181966/contributions/5041437/attachments/2512993/4326863/epol_requirements_sep2022_wilkinson.pdf
Lessons from ILC applied to FCC-ee	Graham Wilson (The University of Kansas (US))	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1181966/contributions/5049882/attachments/2513011/4326709/2209.03281v2.pdf
Beam energy (spread) measurement with dimuons	Patrick Janot (CERN)	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1181966/contributions/5049894/attachments/2512991/4319811/WG4_EnergySpread.pdf
Absolute detector alignment with dimuons	Patrick Janot (CERN)	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1181966/contributions/5049896/attachments/2512994/4319813/WG4_DetectorAlignment.pdf

FCCee Polarization studies with BMAD	Yi Wu (EPFL - Ecole Polytechnique Fédérale Lausanne (CH))	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1181966/contributions/5051868/attachments/2514025/4321752/Yi_EPOL_2022.pdf
Synergies EIC-FCC	Frank Zimmermann (CERN) , Vadim Ptitsyn	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1181966/contributions/5041346/attachments/2514889/4323464/EIC-FCC_Synergy.pptx
Summary and next steps	Alain Blondel (Université de Geneve (CH)) , Guy Wilkinson (University of Oxford (GB)) , Jacqueline Keintzel (CERN)	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1181966/contributions/5041354/attachments/2519671/4332923/Final%20remarks%20and%20next%20steps-AB-2022-09-30.pdf

3.1.2. Launch of User community survey

The questions of the survey aim to delineate the current contribution of different countries in different PED activities and provide data for forecasting how this contribution could evolve in the lifetime of the FCCIS project.

More specifically, the following questions were submitted to the members of the FCC informal forum of national contacts:

1	What were the Physics-Expts and Detectors (PED) Activities in 2021 in your country (type and FTE) ?
2	What is the present situation with the signature of FCC MOU and Addenda for your country ?
3	Are there commitments related to PED ?
4	Relations between PED and the Accelerator community working on FCC ?
5	How is the FCC vs. other ee-colliders situation evolving in your country ?
6	Estimate of the resources (human and funds) that the labs in your country or your national institute plan to commit for FCC PED in 2022 and 2023 ?
7	What are the initiatives to recruit new people and to connect to other groups internationally ?

8	In which domain the additional personpower would engage ?
9	Do you plan a National (or Regional) FCC workshops in 2023 or 2024?
10	Are you building or planning to join a Regional FCC “cluster” with neighbouring nations (cf. Nordic countries) ?
11	Can you list the persons involved at 15% FTE or more in PED activities in your country (presently or within the next 2 years) ?
12	What is the percentage of Male/Female participants in PED activities in your country ?

Responses to these questions have already been received by several countries including Korea, US, Turkey, Finland, Sweden, Denmark, Poland, Czech Republic, Serbia, Germany, Austria, Belgium, United Kingdom, Portugal, Spain, Italy, France and Switzerland. These responses along with those that will be collected during 2023, will be reported in the next milestones M5.5. “Research Programme Consolidated”.

3.2. FUTURE CIRCULAR COLLIDER GLOBAL COLLABORATION WORKING GROUP

In support of the FCC organisation structure approved by the CERN Council in June 2021, FGC Working Group engages with countries with mature communities, a long-standing participation in CERN’s programmes and the potential to contribute substantially to the Organization’s long-term scientific objectives to understand opportunities for national participation through Membership or Associate Membership, as provided by CERN’s geographical enlargement policy, and through long-term bilateral or multilateral agreements.

The FGC Working Group promotes ownership of the feasibility study amongst the participants and FCC/CERN. It facilitates the common interest of co-developing technologies and the interest of the partners to acquire specific technologies through joint activities. It also allows FCC/CERN to develop a high-competency global network in areas that are non-core activities for CERN, such as geology, geodesy, logistics and materials science. The collaboration also allows FCC/CERN to prepare the foundations for industrial research and contributions via national laboratories, research institutes and universities. The collaboration being developed is based on multilateral agreements fostering a global network to exploit synergies instead of creating unnecessary overlap of activities.

This structure federates resources worldwide, forming the core of a globally coordinated strategy of converging activities, involving participants from the European Research Area (ERA) and beyond. Organisations from North America, Asia and Latin America are invited to participate in order to lay the foundations for subsequent development actions that will strengthen the ERA as a focal point of global research cooperation. This worldwide joint effort is also manifested in the continuing participation of the ERA in the long-baseline global neutrino programmes in Japan (Hyper-Kamiokande) and the United States (Long-Baseline Neutrino Facility (LBNF) and the Deep Underground Neutrino Experiment (DUNE)).

This inclusive approach embracing the worldwide science and technology community, in an open and incremental participation process, is the first step to form an international platform for the realisation of a next generation, frontier particle physics research infrastructure, leveraging existing assets and available experience.

In coordination with the FCC organisation structure, the FGC Working Group engages with the participants - national laboratories, research institutes and universities as well as industry in the MS, AMS and NMS - to carry out the following mandate:

- Encourage an expanded membership of participants in the FCC FS.
- Explore opportunities in the FCC FS for future prospective participants.
- Support participants that have made a formal application in a) the process of interacting with the FCC Management, b) clarifying the conditions of membership and c) preparing their presentation to the FCC Collaboration Board.
- Assist the new participants in defining areas in the FCC FS where there is a need for their expertise.
- Conclude relevant agreements for the participation in the FCC FS.
- Facilitate the integration process of new participants once membership is approved.
- Review periodically the process for membership accession (including entry conditions).
- Facilitate the interest of FCC/CERN in the formation of a high-competency network in areas that are non-core activities for CERN, such as geology, geodesy, logistics, and materials science.
- Prepare the foundations for industrial research and contributions via national laboratories, research institutes and universities.
- Liaise and coordinate participation with national contact persons and forums. This includes the continuation of the two-sided approach from the FGC Working Group and from the FCC-PED (Physics, Experiment and Detector) Informal Forum of National Contacts to strengthen the global FCC collaboration.

The current composition of the FGC Working Group remains unchanged from the previous reporting period and is the following:

- Emmanuel Tsesmelis (Convenor)
CERN International Relations
- Michael Benedikt (CERN), Frank Zimmermann (CERN)
FCC Feasibility Study Leader and Deputy
- Alain Blondel (IN2P3 & UNIGE), Patrick Janot (CERN)
FCC PED Coordinators
- John Ellis (King's College London), Panagiotis Charitos (CERN)
FCC Coordination Group
- Gregorio Bernardi (IN2P3), Tadeusz Lesiak (IFJ PAN), Marcin Chrzaszcz (IFJ PAN)
Convenors of FCC-PED Informal Forum of National Contacts

3.2.1. Future Circular Collider GCWP meetings

One of the instruments created with the launch of the FGC Working Group is the FCC Engagement Meetings, providing extended forums with interested countries to discuss collaboration opportunities with the FCC FS.

The meetings include presentations and discussions on the topics of introducing the FCC FS; FCC physics, experiment, detector, accelerator and global collaborations; and presentations from the country-specific community on their expertise and interests in the FCC FS.

Since the launch of the FGC Working Group, the following FCC Engagement Meetings have been organised:

- Mexico - 21 June 2021
- Republic of Korea - 3 September 2021
- Pakistan - 14 September 2021
- Portugal - 26 November 2021
- Estonia - 02 March 2022

while further meetings are planned for 2023. Much interest has been expressed by participating countries and the FCC looks forward to stronger and deeper involvement via follow-up activities.

3.2.2. Expanded FCC FC membership

Participation in the FCC FS is through a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) and Addenda. The updated FCC MoU for the FCC FS has been sent for consideration to all current participating institutes that took part in the previous phase of the FCC study, and the template for Addenda for the FCC FS phase is also being updated. The current participating institutes who wish to take part in FCC FS can continue to participate on the basis of the previously signed MoU until the updated MoU for the FCC FS signed.

The new members of the FCC FS collaboration that have joined in 2021 and 2022:

- Österreichisches Institut für Wirtschaftsforschung (WIFO), Austria, June 2022
- Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB), Belgium, November 2021, PED
- Canadian Light Source (CLS) & University of Saskatchewan, Canada, November 2021, FCC-ee injector
- National Institute for Chemical Physics and Biophysics, Estonia, April 2022
- University of Tartu, Estonia, April 2022
- Tallinn University of Technology, Estonia, April 2022
- NPM Silmet OÜ, Estonia, April 2022
- Testonica Lab OÜ, Estonia, April 2022
- GScan OÜ, Estonia, April 2022
- HIP Helsinki Institute of Physics, Finland, January 2021, Accelerator RF and particle physics
- University of Hamburg (UHH-MIN), Germany, June 2022
- Hellenic Open University (HOU), Greece, November 2022
- University of Thessaly (UTH), Greece, November 2022
- Institute for Research in Fundamental Science (IPM), Iran, May 2022
- University of Tehran (UT), Iran, April 2022
- UAS Universidad Autónoma de Sinaloa, Mexico, July 2021, FCC-hh injector.
- Pakistan Atomic Energy Commission (PAEC), Pakistan, June 2022
- Laboratory of Instrumentation and Experimental Particle Physics (LIP), Portugal, November 2021, PED and ACCEL
- Physik-institut (UZH), Switzerland, October 2022
- Chiang Mai University, Thailand, November 2022

NB: members who joined after December 2021 must be approved by the International Collaboration Board.

4. PRESENTATIONS IN CONFERENCES

4.1. PARTICIPATION IN PHYSICS CONFERENCES

Dates	Conference	Number of Talks	Link
26 to 30 July 2021	European Physical Society Conference on High Energy Physics	18	https://fcc-ee-conference.web.cern.ch/database/conference/914/
7 to 12 June 2021	Weak Interactions and Neutrinos 2021	5	https://fcc-ee-conference.web.cern.ch/database/conference/915/
7 to 10 January 2021	XXVII Cracow EPIPHANY Conference on Future of Particle Physics	7	https://indico.cern.ch/event/934666/timetable/#20210110.detailed
18 to 26 February 2021	XIX international workshop on neutrino telescopes 2021	1	https://fcc-ee-conference.web.cern.ch/database/conference/917/
27 March to 3 April 2021	Rencontre de Moriond 2021: QCD & High Energy Interactions	1	https://fcc-ee-conference.web.cern.ch/database/conference/918/
April 17, 2021-April 20, 2021	APS April Meeting 2021	1	https://fcc-ee-conference.web.cern.ch/database/conference/919/
28 June to 2 July 2021	FCC Week 2021	21	https://indico.cern.ch/event/995850/
6 to 8 July 2021	LISHEP 2021	1	https://fcc-ee-conference.web.cern.ch/database/conference/921/
23 to 28 August 2021	SUSY 2021	8	https://indico.cern.ch/event/875077/timetable/#20210823
12 to 14 July 2021	2021 Meeting of the Division of Particles and	1	https://fcc-ee-conference.web.cern.ch/database/conference/923/

	Fields of the American Physical Society		
15 to 17 September 2021	Matter To The Deepest	1	http://indico.if.us.edu.pl/event/9/session/7/contribution/29
5-9 December 2022	FCCIS workshop	58	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1203316
28 Nov -2 Dec 2022	QCD@LHC 2022	1	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1150707/
7-11 Nov 2022	Higgs 2022	4	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1086716/
31 Oct- 4 Nov 2022	Searching for LLP at LHC and beyond	1	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1166678/
26-28 Oct	24th International Particle Physics Outreach Group Meeting	1	https://ippog.org/events/24th-international-particle-physics-outreach-group-meeting
17-21 Oct	FIPS 2022	1	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1119695/
16-21 Oct	PSI2022	2	https://indico.psi.ch/event/11742/
5-7 Oct	ECFA Workshop on e+e- Higgs/EWK/Top Factories 2022	2	https://indico.desy.de/event/33640/
23 September	ECFA HTE meeting on Z pole physics	1	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1196494/
5-9 December 2022	FCCIS workshop	58	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1203316

4.2. LIST OF TALKS

- Dec. 5, 2022: The case for FCC-ee
- Dec. 4, 2022: Review of FCC physics
- Dec. 2, 2022: QCD at future e+e- colliders
- Nov. 11, 2022: Prospects for Higgs measurements at future e+e- colliders
- Nov. 7, 2022: Electron Yukawa from s-channel resonant Higgs production at FCC-ee
- Nov. 7, 2022: Measuring the Higgs Trilinear Self-Coupling at the FCC-ee

- Nov. 7, 2022: Higgs physics at the FCC
- Nov. 7, 2022: Precise Higgs mass measurements and cross section measurements at the FCC-ee
- Nov. 4, 2022: FCC-ee: Physics and Detector R&D
- Nov. 1, 2022: LLPs at the FCCee
- Oct. 26, 2022: FCC physics goals
- Oct. 17, 2022: Opportunities for FIPs searches at FCC-ee
- Oct. 16, 2022: Precision and rare electroweak physics studies at FCC-ee
- Oct. 16, 2022: Precision flavour and tau physics at FCC-ee
- Oct. 5, 2022: Measuring the Higgs Trilinear Self-Coupling at the FCC-ee
- Oct. 5, 2022: Prospects of B_c^+ , $B^+ \rightarrow \tau \nu$ decays at FCC-ee
- Sept. 23, 2022: Overview of the e^+e^- Z pole programme
- Sept. 12, 2022: (Higgs) Physics at Future colliders
- Sept. 12, 2022: High-precision EW and QCD physics at FCC-ee
- Sept. 12, 2022: Status of detector requirements for FCC-ee
- Sept. 12, 2022: Searches for feebly interacting new particles at FCC-ee
- Sept. 6, 2022: Status and physics potential of FCC-ee
- Aug. 29, 2022: Physics studies at FCC-ee
- Aug. 29, 2022: The FCC project: physics and machine state-of-the-art
- Aug. 29, 2022: High-precision QCD physics a FCC/FCC-ee
- Aug. 25, 2022: FCC overview
- July 31, 2022: Heavy neutrino production at the FCC-ee: Dirac or Majorana?
- July 18, 2022: High-precision EW physics at FCC-ee
- July 9, 2022: Flavour and tau physics at FCC-ee
- July 9, 2022: Searches for feebly interacting new particles at FCC-ee
- July 8, 2022: Higgs physics at the FCC: the stunning complementarity between ee and pp
- July 8, 2022: Status of detector requirements for FCC-ee
- July 8, 2022: The IDEA detector concept for FCCee
- July 8, 2022: Precise Higgs mass measurements and cross section measurements at the FCC-ee
- July 7, 2022: EWK precision measurements at FCC
- July 6, 2022: FCC-ee Energy Calibration and Polarization
- July 6, 2022: High-precision QCD physics at FCC-ee
- July 6, 2022: Heavy neutrino production at the FCC-ee: Dirac or Majorana?
- July 6, 2022: Jet flavour tagging at FCC-ee
- June 17, 2022: FCC Physics Prospects
- June 17, 2022: FCC accelerator and detector aspects
- June 9, 2022: Prospects of B_c^+ and $B^+ \rightarrow \tau \nu$ decays at FCC-ee
- May 31, 2022: High-precision QCD physics at FCC-ee
- May 20, 2022: Physics at future e^+e^- colliders
- May 19, 2022: Experiments at future hadron colliders
- May 19, 2022: Physics at Future Hadron Colliders
- May 6, 2022: QCD at FCC-ee

- Jan. 11, 2022: Electron Yukawa determination at FCC-ee
- Jan. 11, 2022: Higgs measurements at the Future Circular Colliders

ANNEX:

Put any additional information such as detailed drawings, figures, larger tables, additional information in an unnumbered annex.

20/12/2022, 15:40

FCCIS M5.3 survey

FCCIS M5.3 survey

A user community survey on R&D topics, priorities and collaboration potentials considering geographical distribution and topical complementarity launched.

* Required

Status of collaboration

The following questions aim to help us understand the status of collaboration with the FCC activities since the launch of the study.

1. Have you previous worked on collider-based experiments? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 No

2. If yes, could you please give more information on your previous research work?

3. Have you previously been involved in the design of linear colliders?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 No

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FCCIS M5.3 survey

4. Have you previously been involved in the FCC activities? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

5. If yes, could you please specify in which activities?

6. Is your institute a member of the FCC Collaboration having signed the FCC MOU? *

Mark only one oval.

Signed MoU

Process of signature an MoU has been launched.

No MoU

Other: _____

7. Has your institute signed an Addenda with FCC?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

8. If yet, could you please give us more detail about the scope of the work?

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FCCIS M5.3 survey

9. Are you building or planning to join a Regional FCC “cluster” with neighboring nations (cf. Nordic countries) ?

Check all that apply.

YES

NO

Contribution on the
PED activities of
FCC-ee

Capturing the experimental goals of the FCC-ee that
attract the most interest among the communities

10. Is there a research topic that should be strengthened in the proposed FCC-ee physics programme?

11. Which research could largely profit from the complementarity between FCC-ee and FCC-hh machines?

12. Which research topic could largely profit from the complementarity between FCC-ee and linear lepton colliders (ILC/CLIC)?

Mark only one oval.

Option 1

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FCCIS M5.3 survey

13. In which of the following FCC-ee research areas you would consider contributing in the future? *

Check all that apply.

- Electroweak
 Top physics
 Flavour
 Higgs
 Other: _____

14. Are you currently working in any of these areas?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 No

15. Which of the following research areas of the FCC-ee programme offer the greatest value?

Mark only one oval.

- Higgs studies
 Electroweak observables precision studies
 Top physics
 Flavour physics
 Feebly interacting particles
 Other (please specify)

Hardware R&D efforts

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FCCIS M5.3 survey

16. Have you previously worked in detector R&D *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

17. If you answered NO, how likely is that you or a member of a group shift to that direction

Mark only one oval.

Very unlikely

1

2

3

4

5

Certainly is going to happen

18. What are your current R&D research objectives? *

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FCCIS M5.3 survey

19. Vertex detectors *

Mark only one oval.

Not interested

1

2

3

4

5

Interested

20. PID detectors

Mark only one oval.

Not interested

1

2

3

4

5

Interested

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FCCIS M5.3 survey

21. Tracking detectors

Mark only one oval.

Not interested

1

2

3

4

5

Interested

22. EM Calorimeter

Mark only one oval.

Not intered

1

2

3

4

5

Interested

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FCCIS M5.3 survey

23. Hadronic Calorimeter

Mark only one oval.

Not interested

1

2

3

4

5

Interested

24. Other R&D interests (provide which ones)

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FCCIS M5.3 survey

25. Online software

Mark only one oval.

Not Interested

1

2

3

4

5

Interested

26. Offline software

Mark only one oval.

Not Interested

1

2

3

4

5

Interested

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FCCIS M5.3 survey

27. Monte Carlo Generators

Mark *only one* oval.

Not Interested

1

2

3

4

5

Interested

28. In which domain you think that additional person power should engage?

Mark *only one* oval.

- R&D
- Physics Analysis
- Computing
- Software

29. Do you think that R&D activities in the framework of detectors for linear colliders could apply in FCC-ee?

Mark *only one* oval.

- Yes
- No

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FCCIS M5.3 survey

30. In your opinion, which is one of the biggest experimental challenges for the FCC-ee detectors?

Future steps

31. Continent you are from

Mark only one oval.

- Europe
 North America
 South America
 Asia
 Africa

32. How could FCC get more involvement from your country?

33. Have you previously collaborated with other research laboratories in the framework of an R&D project?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 No

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FCCIS M5.3 survey

34. In which countries you have identified potential collaborators on an FCC R&D topic?

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